

Book Review**OF**

Mitchell N. Berman & Richard D. Friedman

The Jurisprudence of Sport: Sports and Games as Legal Systems

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Sports Law as a practice area of law is still in very nascent age and as a subject has still not been taught as major area of law in any jurisdiction so far. It was in 2011 when Mitchell N Berman who is also the author of this book introduced 'jurisprudence of sport' nomenclature. JOS is not only an area of study or practice area of law but it is also a way of studying how law works in sports arena. From time immemorial all sports are been governed by some or other area of rules which have been defined and set as long the sport has been in existence and are upgraded along with time keeping in view the needs of the particular sport. Sports and the rules in which it operates is altogether an entire set of laws and principles which govern it and a very rich area of study. Various sports and its rules is a challenging study for lawyers.

As an area of study JOS defines and explains various legal aspects which help in solving complex and difficult problems of sports by analysis of underlying rules. JOS provide us with rich insights into nuances of games in the realm under which they works. Since the Olympian games of ancient times the athletes have been sworn an oath to upkeep the sportsman spirit and follow the rules and las as set for the game. This oath is a consent both implied and express as it creates an obligation on athlete to conduct himself in defined set of rules.The obligation in sports is dual one political which can be resolved by normative system i.e. oath taken by athlete to follow rules or a consent among participants to uphold rule of game.When one obligation under consent fails normative system comes into picture. Sportsmanship , game spirit and fair play are subset of dedication toward game and its rules.

David Fraser (1993) was of view that Hans Kelsengrundnorm (basic norm) in sports is fair play . The basic norm tries to explain how the normative system works in sports. It further tries to explain how fair play leads to fair competition. The writer also explains how the normative system takes care of various patterns of game and equivalency of participant by categorising them in various sub categories based on sex , age and weights(combative games such as wrestling and boxing).

In 1992 legal eagle David Fraser came out with a publication “Cricket and the Law’ wherein the author had tried to provide an in depth analysis of cricket and its rules. Early Jurist and Scholars like Hart , Raz in many places had held that sports is an area where new and challenging legal issues will arise and there will be a need to interpret and form rules to govern it. In 2003, a German collection of essays was published, entitled ‘Recht und Spielregeln’ (Law and Game Rules), edited by Andreas von Arnould which was one of landmark in history of literature related to sports law .

Structure of the book

In Chapter 1 page 4 , author who are well know legal scholars also state that the sports teaches us many things about it by analysing hard about law and sports. The book comprises of 601 pages with 5 parts and 17 chapters which in a way reflects how well have author tried to cover the entire sports jurisprudence extensively for students .Though the primary audience of book is students but it is also a good resource for researchers and scholars working in field of Jurisprudence. Though the book is a comprehensive piece of work we will breakdown it in Parts to understand the objective of the book and thoughts of eminent scholars who wrote the book.

Part I of Book, ‘Fundamentals’ is about what is common understanding of sport and game while Part II ‘Structuring the Competition” is how a game is designed and what are important ground rules for it. Part III , ‘Officiating” talks about the referees , umpires and officials who coordinate and regulate the game under set norms. It also looks at various tools employed for checking , replaying and correcting errors committed by referees and umpires. It accounts into human errors and new age technology for coming to its aid for correcting such errors. Part IV i.e. ‘Playing the Game’ looks into various concepts ofsportsmanship, team spirit , foul and cheating. Part V , ‘Outside the line’ is two dimensional theory about conduct and

regulations of athletes as well as maintenance of records and honors of various games, championships awarded to athletes.

The book is one of the most comprehensive work of law about sports. It not only speaks volume about the game but also its conduct and regulations. It might sound theoretical but for a legal student it poses a challenge to understand the concepts and its application keeping in view of complex nature and essence of sport. The author has scholarly challenged legal students to take up academic legal research and write a justification in a memo for local newspaper as to why cigar-smoking competitions are not sporting events. This kind of challenge not only quenches the thirst of students but also exposes them into reason and evidence based research on practical issues.

Chapter 2 dwells into the case *PGA Tour, Inc. v. Martin*, 532 U.S. 661 (2001) which went all the way to US Supreme court involving the applicability of the Americans with Disabilities Act of 1990 to professional golf tours. The PGA Tour organizers were of the view that the game is all about walking between shots to play the game and no usage of golf cart is allowed, which according to them was an important aspect of the game. Golfer Casey Martin, whose circulatory condition impaired his ability to walk, sued the PGA Tour under the ADA, asserting that it must accommodate his disability by allowing him to use a golf cart. The Supreme Court ruled for Martin in a 7–2 decision. The court found that the PGA Tour should be viewed as a commercial enterprise operating in the entertainment industry for the economic benefit of its members rather than as a private club. It agreed with the Magistrate Judge Thomas Coffin that the statutory definition of public accommodation included a "golf course", rejecting the Tour's argument that its competitions are only places of public accommodation in the areas open to spectators. The operator of a public accommodation could not, in Judge Coffin's view, create private enclaves within the facility "... and thus relegate the ADA to hop-scotch areas." The finding was originally upheld by the United States Court for the Ninth Circuit. The author in the Chapter provides reasoning used by majority decision as well as dissenting opinion and even in case of game its versatile nature and essence views can differ of jurists. The chapter also highlights issues which arise because of this case in 'comments and questions' section.

Chapter 3, Authors look into various goals and problems faced for fair conduct of games. The authors take into account seven issues viz (1) promotion of fair competition ; (2)

encouragement , training and rewarding of sporting skills ; (3) presenting optimal challenges; (4) encouraging excitement; (5) making sure that there is uniform challenge across various categories; (6) making appropriate arrangements for safer and health of participants; and (7) framing rules which are immediately applicable.

The author dwells upon prospectiveness of the rules and why the same cannot be applied retrospectively. It touches the issues as to how in previous times rules were framed retrospectively by Nazis and Argentinian generals to grant them immunity under rule of law which was declared null and void years later based on jurisprudence. The book speaks volume about sports which have significantly based on normative jurisprudence, The games not only includes team sports like cricket , soccer , hockey ,baseball but also individual games like chess, boxing and gymnastics as well as competitive eating.

The author has brought in Chapter 7 a topic which have been till now remain untouched in any of previous literature i.e. ‘Sex and Gender’ .The author argues that the discrimination which leads to exclusion based on sex is justified in sports. Parry &Martínková (2021) contends that it actually do not exclude but in reality it facilitates ‘maximum inclusion’s.

Berman & Friedman write (p. 247): *“allowing weight classes permits a wider range of athletes to take part in a sport. In boxing, for example, were there no weight classes there would be many fewer professional or amateur boxers participating in competitive matches because, by and large, a person who is featherweight would lose to a heavyweight, even if the latter were of considerably lower talent”*.

The author also discusses intersex athletes and those of transgender in great details.This area for long has been considered a debatable topic but due to emerging jurisprudence and cases now this reading is useful.

The authors write (page 265): *“It is also important to know that any strength and endurance advantages a transgender woman arguably may have as a result of her prior testosterone levels dissipate after about one year of estrogen or testosterone-suppression therapy. According to medical experts on this issue, the assumption that a transgender woman competing on a women’s team would have a competitive advantage outside the range of*

performance and competitive advantage or disadvantage that already exists among female athletes is not supported by evidence”.

As per research (World Rugby 2020, Pike 2020, Hilton & Lundberg 2021, Harper et al 2021) It have been proven in many scientific research that after male puberty there is a considerable performance advantage and even after one year continuous intake of testosterone suppressing drugs the performance advantage remains. Another study (Roberts et al, 2021) shows that female athletes can catch up with male counterparts if they pursue a hormonal treatment for estrogens and in some cases outperform their peers. One case quoted by author is ‘the number of sit-ups performed in 1 min by transmen exceeded the average performance of their male counterparts’. In the past German female athletes have been found to enhance their performance by usage of synthetic testosterone however the same do not work for the opposite sex i.e. reduction of testosterone in males do lead to any enhancement in their performance.

In their study Parry & Martíňková (2021) differentiates between advantages due to categorisation and advantages arising due to competition. Some well established athlete have clear advantage as they have tolerable margin of wins wherein there is a fair chance of any other athlete to take over them.

International Olympics Committee has been accepted transgender athletes in various categories of games with a condition that their gender is legally recognised. If in legal documents their biological gender has been assigned from ‘male’ to ‘female’ it make them formally eligible to compete in female category. Having said that , it is contended by many that by reassigning the gender or by virtue of any treatment only gender is changed however the physiology remains the same. This creates a legal fiction (*fictiolegis*) which goes back to roman law in mind of trainers, lawyers and legal professionals.

Martíňková et al 2021 contends that we are categorising as per gender but the transwomen eligibility should be further examined. In UK and Australia law excludes the rights of transwomen athletes from female category except in such case wherein state recognises the transwomen as women in all respects. This rule of legislation is based on legal fiction (*fictiolegis*) which makes a basis for exclusion whereas in other legislation there is no such exclusion allowed thereby allowing transwomen to compete in female category. In a recent

change of stance IOC has ruled that their will no longer be need of reducing testosterone level by transwomen. This ruling is based on premise that ‘*there should be no presumption that trans women have an automatic advantage over natal women*’. However right this ruling may sound but the reason for same opens a whole new set of issues such as Human Rights since the act of changing natural hormonal structure is bound to have long term complications in human body. The author subtly touches this theme in this section while harping on unnecessary policy on testosterone level by some sports governing bodies.

In page 269 author takes a glance briefly on issue of considering sports as a human right (IOC stance) and whether discrimination or segregation or classification and categorisation is a right for trans athletes to compete in sex category of their gender.

Conclusion

The book though very long of 625 pages keeping in view of young generation lawyers provides a very strong ground for law students. It not only covers various sports and its philosophies but changes in rules of games also appeal to student as to how keeping in view of need of times rules are framed and reframed to suit current needs. The book discusses various aspects of conservatism as well as innovation in sports and is a very resourceful guide for sports authorities. Overall book leaves a very good impression in mind of readers who wish to take their knowledge of sports level to another level.

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